

COMMUNAL STATE INSTITUTION "EDUCATION DEPARTMENT OF THE CITY OF ALMATY"

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To: SmartUp School

The Education Department of the city of Almaty, having reviewed your letter, informs that it does not object to the implementation of the SmartUp School giftedness development technology in secondary education organizations. However, a mandatory condition for the implementation of the technology is the coordination with the school principals.

Furthermore, information regarding the SmartUp School giftedness development technology has been forwarded to the district education departments and secondary education organizations for their information.

Deputy Head

(Signature)

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